

Part I : Filtering and Data Association

Part II : Crowd-scene Analysis

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Bob Collins, July 2012

What is Tracking?

typical idea: tracking a single target in isolation.

Appearance-Based Tracking

Appearance-based Tracking

Research tends to focus on:

- finding discriminative features
- model adaptation

Search for best match tends to be simple gradient ascent (hill-climbing).

Motion prediction tends to be simplified to constant position + noise (assumes previous bounding box significantly overlaps object in the new frame).

Previous VLPR lectures with more detail:

<http://www.cse.psu.edu/~rcollins/CollinsVLPR2009Lecture.pdf>

<http://www.cse.psu.edu/~rcollins/CollinsVLPR2010Lecture.pdf>

What is Tracking?

Multi-target tracking....

ant behavior, courtesy of
Georgia Tech biotracking

“targets” can be corners, and
tracking gives us optic flow.

What is Tracking?

articulated objects having
multiple, coordinated parts

Multi-Target Tracking

- The previous two slides are examples of tracking multiple targets over time. Such work tends to focus on constraints between individuals, either strong geometric constraints, or weak exclusion constraints.

What is Tracking?

Active tracking involves moving the sensor in response to motion of the target. Needs to be real-time!

Why are there so many papers on tracking?

Because what kind of tracking “works”
depends on problem-specific factors.

Factors: Discriminability

How easy is it to discriminate one object from another.

~~appearance models can
do all the work~~

constraints on geometry
and motion become crucial

Factors: Frame Rate

H
I
G
H

frame n

frame n+1

gradient ascent
(e.g. mean-shift)
works OK

frame 2325: nmatch 7 nmissed 0 nfalse 0

frame 2375: nmatch 6 nmissed 0 nfalse 0

L
O
W

much harder
search problem.
data association

Other Factors

single target vs multiple targets

single camera vs multiple cameras

on-line vs batch-mode

do we have a good generic detector?
(e.g. faces; pedestrians)

does object have multiple parts?

Filtering and Data Association

- Filtering
 - Recursive Bayesian estimation
 - (continuous) Probability Theory
- Data Association
 - Assignment problems
 - (discrete) Combinatorics

State Space Approach

Two vectors of interest:

1) State vector: vector of variables x_k representing what we want to know about the target

examples: $[x,y]$; $[x,y,dx,dy]$; $[x,y,\theta,scale]$

2) Measurement vector: noisy observations z_k related to the state vector.

examples: image intensity/color; motion blobs

Foundation: Bayesian Filtering

Rigorous general framework for tracking. Estimates the values of an unknown state vector given a time series of uncertain observations.

Key idea: use a recursive estimator to incrementally update the posterior probability density function (pdf) of the state vector based on most recent data.

Bayesian hypothesis: All quantities of interest, such as MAP or marginal estimates, can be computed from the posterior pdf.

Bayes Rule

Bayes rule can be derived by a simple manipulation of the rules of probability. But it has far-reaching consequences.

$$p(x, y) = p(x|y)p(y) = p(y|x)p(x)$$

$$p(x|y) = \frac{p(y|x)p(x)}{p(y)} = \frac{p(y|x)p(x)}{\int_x p(y|x)p(x)}$$

interpretation:

posterior \propto likelihood * prior

Thomas Bayes
1702-1761

Posterior Distribution

For a Bayesian, the posterior distribution is the starting point for answering all well-posed statistical questions about the state.

e.g.

- What is the most likely location of this object?
the mode of the posterior (MAP estimate)
- With what certainty do I know that location?
spread of probability mass around the MAP estimate
- Are there other likely locations? If so, how many?
analysis of multi-modality of the posterior

Important point: output of Bayesian approach is not a single point estimator, but a whole probability distribution over state values.

A Simple “Cartoon” Example

Let’s assume our target state x is a 2D location (x_1, x_2) , and that our target is within some bounded region of interest, say

$$0 < x_1 < 100 \text{ and } 0 < x_2 < 100$$

Bearings-Only Example

Initially we don't know the target is, so we guess it is at (50,50).
We are uncertain, so model that uncertainty as a Gaussian with high variance (truncated and normalized so all mass lies within the region of interest)

Bearings-Only Example

A bearings-only sensor located at $(0,0)$ takes a noisy reading of the angle (alpha) towards the target. We will model the difference between the measured angle and actual angle as a zero-mean, 1D Gaussian.

Bearings-Only Example

prior

likelihood

to combine using Bayes rule: point-wise multiply the prior times the likelihood, then renormalized the result so that total mass sums up to 1.

Bearings-Only Example

prior

likelihood

posterior

Bearings-Only Example

Say a second sensor at $(0,100)$ also takes a second noisy measurement of the target. We this have another likelihood function to represent this second observation.

Bearings-Only Example

prior = our
old posterior

new posterior

likelihood

becomes prior for
new observations

A More Interesting Example

Let's say our ship wants to be found, and is broadcasting a radio signal, picked up by a transmitter on a buoy. That gives us a known distance to the ship.

A second, bearings-only reading, is also taken...

Range+Bearings Example

Range+Bearings Example

prior
 $p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}_1)$

$p(\mathbf{z}_2|\mathbf{x})$
likelihood

posterior

$$p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2) = \frac{p(\mathbf{z}_2|\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}_1)}{\sum_{\mathbf{x}} p(\mathbf{z}_2|\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z}_1)}$$

Range+Bearings Example

Note the posterior distribution is multimodal. Presumably a second bearings reading from a sensor at the lower left of the region would disambiguate the location. But it is important that the multimodality be preserved, in order for that to happen! If we only kept the highest peak (in this example), we would get the wrong answer.

posterior

Adding Motion Prediction

Our previous examples left out something important...

We didn't take into account that the target could be moving!

To do this we also need to model $p(x_t | x_{t-1})$

Tracking as Bayesian Estimation

Graphical Model:

Markov assumptions

$$p(x_k | x_0, \dots, x_{k-1}) = p(x_k | x_{k-1})$$

$$p(z_k | x_0, \dots, x_k) = p(z_k | x_k)$$

Factored joint probability distribution

$$p(x_0, \dots, x_k, z_1, \dots, z_k) = p(x_0) \prod_{i=1}^k p(z_i | x_i) p(x_i | x_{i-1})$$

Recursive Bayes Filter

Motion Prediction Step:

predicted current state **state transition** **previous estimated state**

$$\underline{p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1})} = \int p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}) p(\mathbf{x}_{k-1} | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1}) d\mathbf{x}_{k-1}.$$

Data Correction Step (Bayes rule):

estimated current state **measurement** **predicted current state**

$$\underline{p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k})} = \frac{p(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{x}_k) p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1})}{\underline{p(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1})}}$$

↓ **normalization term**

$$\underline{p(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1})} = \int p(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{x}_k) p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1}) d\mathbf{x}_k$$

Problem

Except in special cases, these integrals are intractable.

Motion Prediction Step:

$$p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1}) = \int p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}) p(\mathbf{x}_{k-1} | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1}) d\mathbf{x}_{k-1}.$$

Data Correction Step (Bayes rule):

$$p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k}) = \frac{p(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{x}_k) p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1})}{p(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1})}$$

$$p(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1}) = \int p(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{x}_k) p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{z}_{1:k-1}) d\mathbf{x}_k$$

Such Special Cases

All pdfs are Gaussian → Kalman Filtering

Monte Carlo Integration → Particle Filtering; MCMC

Hill-climbing on posterior → Mean-Shift; Lucas-Kanade

and of course there are lots
of papers on all of these

Filtering and Data Association

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Intro to Data Association

Let's consider a different tracking approach

- Detect objects in each frame.
- Determine interframe correspondences between them.

Actually, in “ancient” times when tracking meant looking at blips on a radar screen, this was the natural approach.

It is popular again due to successes in object detection.

Remainder of this Talk

- Data Association
 - associate two sets of objects
 - e.g. matching detections across frames
- Two frames: linear assignment problem
- Generalize to three or more frames

- Greedy Method
 - Mincost Network Flow
 - Multidimensional Assignment ← **NP-hard**
- } **Polynomial time**

**increasing
solution
quality**

↓ approximate solution

R.Collins, "Multitarget Data Association with Higher-Order Motion Models," *CVPR 2012*.

Data Association Scenarios

Match object detections across frames

Data Association Scenarios

Match a current set of trajectories to object detections in the next frame

How to determine which observations to add to which track?

Linear Assignment Formulation

Form a matrix of
pairwise similarity
scores

Frame T+1

	.11	.95	.23
Frame T	.85	.25	.89
	.90	.12	.81

We want to choose one match from each row and column to maximize sum of scores

Linear Assignment Formulation

Extend each trajectory (motion prediction) and assign scores to each observation based on inverse distance such that closer observations get higher numbers.

choose at most one match in each row and column to maximize sum of scores.

Linear Assignment Problem

Mathematical Definition

maximize: $\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} x_{ij}$

subject to: $\sum_j x_{ij} = 1; \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$
 $\sum_i x_{ij} = 1; \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n$
 $x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$

constraints that say
X is a permutation matrix

The permutation matrix ensures that we only match up one object from each row and from each column.

note: alternately, we can minimize costs rather than maximize weights

minimize: $\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_{ij} x_{ij}$

Hungarian Algorithm

There is an algorithm called Kuhn-Munkres or “Hungarian” algorithm specifically developed to efficiently solve the linear assignment problem.

If you need to solve LAP, you should use it.

However, we are going to look at other algorithms, because they generalize more readily to multi-frame (> 2 frames) problems.

Greedy Solution to LAP

Find the largest score.

Remove scores in same row and column from consideration
(that is, enforcing the 1-1 matching constraints)

Repeat

	1	2	3	4	5
1	0.95	0.76	0.62	0.41	0.06
2	0.23	0.46	0.79	0.94	0.35
3	0.61	0.02	0.92	0.92	0.81
4	0.49	0.82	0.74	0.41	0.01
5	0.89	0.44	0.18	0.89	0.14

$$\text{Score} = .95 + .94 + .92 + .82 + .14 = 3.77$$

Is this the best we can do?

Greedy Solution to LAP

No!

	1	2	3	4	5
1	0.95	0.76	0.62	0.41	0.06
2	0.23	0.46	0.79	0.94	0.35
3	0.61	0.02	0.92	0.92	0.81
4	0.49	0.82	0.74	0.41	0.01
5	0.89	0.44	0.18	0.89	0.14

Greedy Solution

Score=3.77

	1	2	3	4	5
1	0.95	0.76	0.62	0.41	0.06
2	0.23	0.46	0.79	0.94	0.35
3	0.61	0.02	0.92	0.92	0.81
4	0.49	0.82	0.74	0.41	0.01
5	0.89	0.44	0.18	0.89	0.14

Optimal Solution

Score=4.26

Greedy method is easy to program; quick to run; and yields “pretty good” solutions in practice.

But it often does not yield the optimal solution.

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	2	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	4	5	1

Min-Cost Flow

Robert Collins
Penn State

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	2	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	4	5	1

Min-Cost Flow

Min-Cost Flow

transform weights into costs $c_{ij} = \alpha - w_{ij}$

add source/sink nodes with 0 cost

Min-Cost Flow

transform weights into costs $c_{ij} = \alpha - w_{ij}$

add source/sink nodes with 0 cost

directed edges with flow capacity of 1

pump N units of flow from source to sink

Min-Cost Flow

note: interior nodes become transshipment nodes
(sum flow out = sum flow in)

Min-Cost Flow

There are standard algorithms for efficiently solving min-cost network flow, e.g. push-relabel algorithm; or successive shortest paths.

Min-Cost Flow

Nice property: The min-cost flow formalism readily generalizes to matching sets with unequal sizes.

Min-Cost Flow

Min-cost flow formalism readily generalizes to matching between sets with unequal sizes.

Last Words on LAP

- As I mentioned earlier, the solution used in practice is Kuhn-Munkres (aka Hungarian) algorithm.
- Main point is that exact solution to LAP can be found efficiently (in polynomial time).

Remainder of this Talk

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- Two frames: linear assignment problem
- Generalize to three or more frames

- Greedy Method
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- } **Polynomial time**

**increasing
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R.Collins, "Multitarget Data Association with Higher-Order Motion Models," *CVPR 2012*.

Multi-Frame Generalization

Generalizing to three more more frames

- Sequential (Recursive) Greedy Method
- Mincost Network Flow
- Multidimensional Assignment

Increasing generality from top-to-bottom

Sequential Greedy Method

- Extend a partial solution, frame-by-frame, sequentially forwards in time
- Results in a series of linear assignment problems between trajectories found up to frame $t-1$ and new observations in frame t .

Traditional multi-target tracking approach. Often combined with recursive filtering to smooth the trajectories.

For more info: Blackman and Popoli, *Design and Analysis of Modern Tracking Systems*.

Sequential Greedy Matching

Matching observations in a new frame to a set of trajectories from frames 1 to $t-1$

Prediction

Predict next target position along each track via some motion model (e.g. constant velocity).

Prediction / Scoring

Form track i to observation j scores w_{ij} based on distance and (or) appearance such that higher scores mean better matches.

Prediction / Scoring / Solve

Find optimal solution using Hungarian algorithm.

Important Point

Constant velocity motion prediction greatly improves quality of matching in situations where objects are closely spaced and appearance cues are not strong.

Offset of correct match from last known location of object.

Sequential Greedy Method

Pros:

- Very efficient (real-time tracking)

- Very common / well-understood

Cons:

- Purely causal (no “look-ahead”)

- Matches, once made, cannot be undone if later information shows them to be suboptimal

Network Flow Approach

Motivation: Seeking a globally optimal solution by considering observations over all frames in “batch” mode.

Approach: Extend two-frame min-cost formulation by adding observations from all frames into the network

Network Flow Approach

picture from Zhang, Li and Nevatia, “**Global Data Association for Multi-Object Tracking Using Network Flows**,” CVPR 2008.

Network Flow Solutions

- push-relabel method
 - Zhang, Li and Nevatia, “**Global Data Association for Multi-Object Tracking Using Network Flows,**” CVPR 2008.
- successive shortest path algorithm
 - Berclaz, Fleuret, Turetken and Fua, “**Multiple Object Tracking using K-shortest Paths Optimization,**” IEEE PAMI, Sep 2011.
 - Pirsiavash, Ramanan, Fowlkes, “**Globally Optimal Greedy Algorithms for Tracking a Variable Number of Objects,**” CVPR 2011.
 - these both include approximate dynamic programming solutions

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

min-cost flow network

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

min-cost flow network

Find the minimum cost path.

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

min-cost flow network

Find the minimum cost path.

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

min-cost flow network

Reverse each edge along that path, and negate the score on each reverse edge.

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

min-cost flow network

Find a remaining minimum cost path.

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

min-cost flow network

Reverse each edge along that path, and negate the score on each reverse edge.

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

min-cost flow network

Find a remaining minimum cost path.

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

min-cost flow network

Notice that this path includes a reversed edge. When this happens, edit rules are applied to splice and correct the previous and new paths.

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
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min-cost flow network

**Notice that this path includes a reversed edge.
When this happens, edit rules are applied to
splice and correct the previous and new paths.**

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
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min-cost flow network

Reverse each edge along that path, and negate the score on each reverse edge.

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

min-cost flow network

Now we are done, since there are no more directed paths from S to T.

Successive Shortest Path Example

Small (3x3) example

	b1	b2	b3
a1	3	1	3
a2	2	1	3
a3	6	5	1

corresponding
solution

min-cost flow network

maximum weight matching (thick edges).
Total weight = 11

Network Flow

Pros:

Efficient (polynomial time)

Uses all frames to achieve a global batch solution

Cons:

Cost function is limited to pairwise terms

Cannot represent constant velocity or other higher-order motion models

Will therefore have trouble when appearance information is not discriminative and/or frame rate is low

Confusion Alert

- Wait... we know the graphical model for Kalman filter has only pairwise links, yet KF is able to represent constant velocity motion models. Why do you say a network flow graph cannot?

- KF is a recursive estimator that can propagate past location information forward in time. Network flow graphs are static structures; costs on edges are fixed in advance, but constant velocity is a function of 3 nodes (if only x,y data observed).

Multi-Dimensional Assignment

Recall the elements of 2D assignment problem:

- observations are nodes in bipartite graph
- edges contain one node from each partite set
- each edge has an associated cost / weight
- each edge has a binary decision variable (on/off)
- each node can only be part of one “on” edge
(i.e. edges in the solution set are disjoint)

Multi-Dimensional Assignment

Generalization to k-frame assignment problem:

- observations are nodes in k-partite graph
- hyperedges contain one node from each partite set
- each hyperedge has an associated cost / weight
- each hyperedge has a binary decision variable
- hyperedges in solution set must be disjoint

Four-Frame Example

observations arranged in four sets (4-partite graph)

Four-Frame Example

hyperedge 1-2-2-3 { decision variable x_{1223}
associated cost c_{1223}

Four-Frame Example

hyperedges 1-2-2-3 and 3-2-3-2 are incompatible

- they share observation 2 in frame 2
- $x_{1223} + x_{3232} > 1$ is disallowed

Four-Frame Example

1-2-2-3 , 3-3-3-2 , 2-1-1-1 is a feasible solution

- all observations used once and only once [partitioning]
- $x_{1223} = x_{3332} = x_{2111} = 1$; all others 0
- solution cost is $c_{1223} + c_{3332} + c_{2111}$

Four-Frame Example

- Mathematical formulation (an ILP)

$$\begin{array}{ll} \min & \sum_{a=0}^{n_a} \sum_{b=0}^{n_b} \sum_{c=0}^{n_c} \sum_{d=0}^{n_d} c_{abcd} x_{abcd} \\ \text{s.t} & Ax = 1 \\ & x \in \{0, 1\} \end{array}$$

Intuition:

We want to find a minimum cost partitioning of observations into disjoint hyperedges.

Some Implementation Details

I am glossing over some details. For example, each partite set includes a dummy node (index 0) that can be assigned multiple times to allow objects to appear, disappear, and to explain missing observations.

This is why we are able to require a partitioning of the observations (each observation used once and only once)

General MDA as an ILP

$$\min \sum_{i_1=0}^{n_1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{n_2} \cdots \sum_{i_k=0}^{n_k} c_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_k} x_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_k}$$

subject to

$$\sum_{i_2=0}^{n_2} \sum_{i_3=0}^{n_3} \cdots \sum_{i_k=0}^{n_k} x_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_k} = 1; \quad i_1 = 1, 2, \dots, n_1$$

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^{n_1} \sum_{i_3=0}^{n_3} \cdots \sum_{i_k=0}^{n_k} x_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_k} = 1; \quad i_2 = 1, 2, \dots, n_2$$

⋮

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^{n_1} \sum_{i_2=0}^{n_2} \cdots \sum_{i_{k-1}=0}^{n_{k-1}} x_{i_1 i_2 \dots i_k} = 1; \quad i_k = 1, 2, \dots, n_k$$

MDA Solutions

- MDA is NP-hard
- three-frame decision version is one of Karp's 21 NP-complete problems
- Previous approaches
 - branch-and-bound: multi-hypothesis tracking (MHT) is a version of this
 - Lagrangian relaxation (Aubrey Poore)
 - complicated, time-consuming algorithms

intuition: there is an exponential number of decision variables that you have to reason about. k objs in f frames $\rightarrow k^f$ hyperedges

Our Approach

- We propose an approximation algorithm
- Starting with an initial feasible solution, it does a series of improvement steps
- Always maintains a feasible solution
- Guaranteed to converge to an optimum
- Caveat: it is a local optimum
- In practice it converges quickly to very reasonable solutions

Factoring Hyperedges

hyperedge 1-2-2-3 \rightarrow (a1-b2) (b2-c2) (c2-d3)

decision variable $x_{1223} = f_{12} * g_{22} * h_{23}$

Factoring Hyperedges

Hyperedges become k-paths; decision variables factor.

Reintroduces graph structure of network flow approach

Key point: factoring allows us to consider local updates!

Factoring Hyperedges

Another important point: costs remain unfactored.

This allows us to use arbitrary cost functions, defined over entire trajectories.

Local Updates

- Pick a pair of adjacent frames (e.g. 2 and 3)

Local Updates

- Pick a pair of adjacent frames (e.g. 2 and 3)
- Revise the decision variables (edges) between those frames while holding the rest of the solution fixed

Local Updates

- Rewriting objective function in terms of edges between frames 2 (indexed by b) and 3 (indexed by c):

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_a \sum_b \sum_c \sum_d c_{abcd} x_{abcd} \\
 &= \sum_a \sum_b \sum_c \sum_d c_{abcd} \underbrace{f_{ab}}_{\text{fixed}} \underbrace{g_{bc}}_{\text{variables being updated}} \underbrace{h_{cd}}_{\text{fixed}} \\
 &= \sum_b \sum_c g_{bc} \sum_a \sum_d f_{ab} h_{cd} c_{abcd} \\
 &= \sum_b \sum_c g_{bc} C_{(a \rightarrow b)bc(c \rightarrow d)} \\
 &= \sum_b \sum_c g_{bc} \omega(b, c)
 \end{aligned}$$

where $(a \rightarrow b)$ means current solution path that ends at observation b in frame 2, and $(c \rightarrow d)$ means current path that starts at observation c in frame 3.

Example

Consider two targets viewed through four frames as in the sketch below:

We are solving for edges between frames 2 and 3 (dashed), holding all other edges (thick) fixed. The reduced cost matrix $w(b,c)$ is:

$$\omega(b, c) = \begin{array}{c} \mathbf{b=1} \\ \mathbf{b=2} \end{array} \begin{array}{cc} \mathbf{c=1} & \mathbf{c=2} \\ \left[\begin{array}{cc} C_{1112} & C_{1121} \\ C_{2212} & C_{2221} \end{array} \right] \end{array}$$

Local Updates

- In the paper, we show that updates to edge decision variables between two adjacent frames:

$$\text{minimize } \sum_a \sum_b \sum_c \sum_d c_{abcd} \underbrace{f_{ab}}_{\text{fixed}} \underbrace{g_{bc}}_{\text{variables being updated}} \underbrace{h_{cd}}_{\text{fixed}}$$

reduces to:

$$\text{minimize } \sum_b \sum_c g_{bc} \omega(b, c)$$

The bottom line is that local updates to edges between two frames reduces to a two-frame linear assignment problem! We solve this using Hungarian algorithm.

To Summarize Our Approach

- Start with an initial feasible solution.

To Summarize Our Approach

- Begin stepping through adjacent pairs of frames, solving updating edge decisions to improve the objective function value

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To Summarize Our Approach

- Step through all pairs of frames, from beginning to end of sequence. This is one cycle.
- If no edge variables changed value during the cycle, we have converged and can stop.
- Otherwise, go back to first pair of frames and step through all pairs for another cycle.

Relation to ICM

- This method is very much related to the iterated conditional modes algorithm of Besag (1986) for computing MAP estimate of an MRF
- But instead of optimizing a single variable at a time, we do a block update of all edge variables between two adjacent frames. [leads to faster convergence, and maintains a feasible solution]
- Inherits convergence properties (and proof) from ICM [guaranteed to converge to a local optimum]

Validation

- Two datasets with ground-truth trajectories collected. One is relatively sparse (average of five people per frame); one is dense (average of 20 people per frame). Each sequence is 15 minutes long.
- We temporally subsampled the data into testsets having 3, 2 and 1 frames per sec.
- Only location data used; no appearance.
- Our approach is compared to two baseline methods
 - greedy sequential filtering (using constant velocity)
 - network flow algorithm (successive shortest paths)

sample frame
dense sequence

Validation

- We use a higher-order trajectory cost function based on the “snake” energy function of Kass, Witkin and Terzopoulos (1987)

$$\text{cost}(P) = \alpha E_{\text{cont}} + \beta E_{\text{curv}}$$

where

$$E_{\text{cont}} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=2}^n \|p_i - p_{i-1}\| \quad \left. \vphantom{\sum} \right\} \text{distance}$$
$$E_{\text{curv}} = \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} \underbrace{\|p_{i+1} - 2p_i + p_{i-1}\|^2}_{\text{curvature}} \quad \left. \vphantom{\sum} \right\} \text{curvature}$$

Sample Results Sparse Dataset

Network Flow
(22 ID swaps)

Our Approach
(2 ID swaps)

Sample Results DenseDataset

Network Flow
(116 ID swaps)

Our Approach
(71 ID swaps)

Validation

- Tabulating mismatch error percentage (one component of the MOTA tracking accuracy measure)

	Sparse Trajectories			Dense Trajectories		
	Flow	Greedy	Ours	Flow	Greedy	Ours
3fps	0.04	0.00	0.00 (1)	0.23	0.12	0.13 (2)
2fps	0.28	0.06	0.12 (1)	1.36	0.34	0.25 (2)
1fps	5.43	1.36	0.80 (2)	21.35	6.83	4.13 (5)

**smaller
numbers
are
better**

$$mmep = 100 \times (\sum_t g(t) / \sum_t mme(t))$$

where $g(t)$ is number of objects at time t and $mme(t)$ is number of ID swaps at time t

Tracking and Data Association

- Tracking
 - Bayesian filtering
 - (continuous) Probability Theory
- Data Association
 - Assignment problems
 - (discrete) Combinatorics

Part I : Tracking and Data Association

Part II : Crowd-scene Analysis

VLPR 2012, Shanghai, China

Bob Collins, July 2012

Crowd Scene Analysis

- Using computer vision tools to look at people in public places
- Real-time monitoring
 - situation awareness
 - notifications/alerts
- After-action review
 - traffic analysis

Crowd Scene Analysis

Things we might want to know:

- How many people are there?
- How to track specific individuals?
- How to determine who is with whom?

Challenges:

Crowd scenes tend to have low resolution.

You rarely see individuals in isolation.

Indeed, there are frequent partial occlusions.

Crowd Counting

FAQ: How many people participated in ...

- **Tahrir Square Protests**
- **Obama's inauguration**
- **Occupy Wall Street**
- **Kumbh Mela**

Jacob's Method

- Herbert Jacobs, Berkeley, 1960s
- count = area * density
 - 10 sqft/person – loose crowd (arm's length from each other)
 - 4.5 sqft/person – more dense
 - 2.5 sqft/person – very dense (shoulder-to-shoulder)
- Problem: Pedestrians do not uniformly distribute over a space, but clump together into groups or clusters.
- Refinement: break area into a grid of ground patches and estimate a different density in each small patch. Accumulate these counts over whole area.

Example of Jacob's Method

source <http://www.popularmechanics.com/science/the-curious-science-of-counting-a-crowd>

Computer Vision Could do Better!

Cavaet: nobody really wants accurate counts

e.g. organizers of the “Million Man March” in Washington DC threatened to sue the National Park Service for estimating that only 400K people attended.

Vision-based Counting

- detection and tracking (light density)
- clustering feature trajectories that move coherently (moderate density)
- treat crowd as a dynamic texture and compute regression estimates based on measured properties (heavy density)

Detecting and Counting Individuals

Ge and Collins, "Marked Point Processes for Crowd Counting," *IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR'09)*, Miami, FL, June 2009, pp.2913-2920.

Good for low-resolution / wide-angle views.

— Relies on foreground/background segmentation.

— Not appropriate for very high crowd density or stationary people.

Crowd Flow/Density

30 minute period

Crowd Flow/Density

movie

Time Lapse. Integrated over spatial/temporal windows.

Motion Segmentation

Idea: track many small features (e.g. corners) over time and cluster sets of features that have similar motion.

corner trajectories

clustering

independently moving objects

- G. J. Brostow and R. Cipolla, “Unsupervised bayesian detection of independent motion in crowds,” in IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2006, pp. 594–601.
- V. Rabaud and S. Belongie, “Counting crowded moving objects,” in IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, New York City, 2006, pp. 705–711.
- D. Sugimura, K. Kitani, T. Okabe, Y. Sato, and A. Sugimoto, “Using individuality to track individuals: Clustering individual trajectories in crowds using local appearance and frequency trait,” in International Conference on Computer Vision, 2009, pp. 1467–1474.

Motion Segmentation

Basic steps: Form a **corner connectivity graph**. Assign each edge a dissimilarity score based on distance and motion coherence of trajectories. Prune edges with high scores. The remaining connected components are the independent objects.

Motion Segmentation

Note: Sugimara et.al. add a feature based on gait periodicity to help disambiguate nearby people.

connectivity graph

connected components after pruning

Texture-based Crowd Detection

Arandjelovic, "Crowd Detection from Still Images," BMVC 2008

- SIFT descriptors
- K-means clustering to form "SIFT-Words"

- Likelihood ratio of distributions of word counts over 10 patch sizes yields 10-D feature vector
- Radial basis SVM for classification into crowd / non-crowd

Texture-based Crowd Detection

Sparse classifications turned into dense segmentation using graph cuts. Unary costs based on SVM output and pairwise costs based on magnitude of patch likelihood scores (small magnitudes indicate interclass boundaries).

Texture-based Counting

Chan and Vasconcelos, "Counting People with Low-level Features and Bayesian Regression",
IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, Vol 21 (4), 2160-2177, April 2012

**motion segmentation
using dynamic textures**

Extract feature vector for each frame:

- **region features**
e.g. area, perimeter, num connected components...
- **internal edge features**
e.g. num edges, histogram of orientations
- **grey-level texture features**
e.g. homogeneity, energy, entropy

Texture-based Counting

Chan and Vasconcelos, "Counting People with Low-level Features and Bayesian Regression",
IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, Vol 21 (4), 2160-2177, April 2012

Extract feature vector for each frame:

estimate counts using
learned regression function

Texture-based Crowd Detection

green/red = crowd walking towards/away blue = total
numeric results formatted as: estimated count (uncertainty) [true count]

Texture-based Crowd Detection

green/red = crowd walking towards/away
numeric results formatted as: estimated count (uncertainty)

Tracking in Dense Crowds

Goal: Track targets in high-density crowd scenes.

**Challenges: lots of occlusion; small object sizes;
appearances are similar**

**Idea: Model typical crowd behavior to provide
better motion priors.**

Point of View: Macro vs Micro

- Macroscopic level: modeling dynamic behavior of the whole crowd; holistic
 - density, flow, mean speed of a traffic stream
 - analogy to fluid streams; particle flow
 - behavior is reactive, a function of environment and density

Crowd Flow

- Microscopic level: models decision makers, their goals, and interactions; individualistic
 - intelligent agents make decisions based on goals and social rules
 - simulating realistic interactions

Social Force Models

Crowd Flow: Floor Fields

Saad Ali and Mubarak Shah, Floor Fields for Tracking in High Density Crowd Scenes, The 10th European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV), 2008.

Inspired by particle flow evacuation models.

Represents how global scene structure affects local pedestrian motion decisions.

Long-range goals/influences transformed into local forces (similar to potential fields for robotic path planning).

potential field

Floor Fields

- **Static Floor Field (SFF)**
attraction field; represents typical crowd motion towards interesting locations, dominant paths, exits
- **Boundary Floor Field (BFF)**
repulsive forces; boundaries, walls, obstacles
- **Dynamic Floor Field (DFF)**
current motion of neighboring individuals computed in temporal sliding window

Static Floor Field

example: marathon runners turning a corner

mean-shift-like procedure
to determine particle flow
(path, distance) to nearest
goal location.

Static Floor Field

example: marathon runners turning a corner

optic flow

(b)
averaged flow over time

(c)
sink-seeking

(d)

**SFF = path length surface.
Low values are “better”.
Intuition: drop a ball on
surface and it rolls towards
nearest sink.**

Boundary Floor Field

(b)
averaged flow

segmented flow

edge map
(real+virtual boundaries)

**BFF = truncated distance transform.
High values are “better”.
Intuition: go/no-go surface with deep
valleys forming the barriers.**

Dynamic Floor Field

local neighborhood around target location (yellow dot)

DFF = current local motion likelihood computed from flow in a narrow temporal window.

Intuition: this is how nearby particles are currently moving.

How Floor Fields are Used

For current target location, compute matrix of local transition probabilities combining appearance and floor field terms.

$$p_{ij} = C e^{k_D D_{ij}} e^{k_S S_{ij}} e^{k_B B_{ij}} R_{ij}$$

SFF/BFF/DFP influence terms (priors)
appearance term (likelihood)

How Floor Fields are Used

**multimodal
likelihood
(appearance is
not discriminative)**

**local motion
prior**

**scene goal
prior**

**much more reliable
(unimodal) posterior**

Tracking Examples

Tracking Examples

Floor Field Drawbacks

- SFF can't represent multimodal goals / motion at single point in the scene

- DFF allows some local temporal adaptation, but only correct when target moves similar to neighbors
- Hard to track outlier behaviors (moving against traffic)

HMM-based Flow Model

Kratz and Nishino, Tracking with Local Spatio-Temporal Motion Patterns in Extremely Crowded Scenes, IEEE Trans Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 2012.

Intuition: model multi-modal, time-varying flow by training an HMM at each scene location.

HMM-based Flow Model

Training stage:

- dice training video into space-time cuboids
- estimate 3D Gaussian motion pattern in each cuboid (space-time gradients)
- in each time-tube of cuboids
 - discretize motion patterns by online clustering
 - train an HMM

HMM-based Flow Model

Training stage:

The HMMs can model time-dependencies between multiple motions at a single spatial location.

e.g. “this location has two dominant flow directions that tend to be interleaved”

“this location exhibits many rapidly-changing flow directions”

“this location has a single dominant flow”

HMM-based Flow Model

Tracking stage:

- at runtime, use observed motion patterns up to time $t-1$ to compute expected motion at target's center at time t .

- project this 3D motion pattern into 2D to get predicted image flow distribution
- use this distribution as a motion prior for particle filter tracking

Sample Results

play video outside ppt

Data Driven Flow Modeling

- Floor fields and HMM-based flow are scene-centric models (must be trained previously on video from the same scene viewpoint)
- They also have trouble tracking “rare” motions because they accumulate distributions of typical scene behavior
- Idea: try non-parametric data-driven approaches that have been very successful in texture synthesis and inpainting.

Data-Driven Flow

Rodriguez, Sivic, Laptev, and Audibert, “Data-driven Crowd Analysis in Videos”, ICCV 2011.

Insight: Any given crowd video can be viewed as a composite mixture of patches taken from a large dataset of previously viewed videos.

Two-Stage Matching

- First stage: Global matching using GIST descriptor of first frame to find videos roughly matching orientation and scale (viewpoint) of input video.

input video

matches from database

Two-Stage Matching

- Second stage: Local patch matching based on HOG3D descriptors (histograms of spatio-temporal gradients) to find patches with similar structure and motion as neighborhood around target.

**spatio-temporal patch
centered on target**

**k-nearest neighbor matches
from pool of stage 1 videos**

Motion Transfer

- Motion information is averaged over the matching patches and incorporated into a motion prior during Kalman filter tracking.
- This data-driven prior, using different videos, does better than averaging scene flow over the actual input sequence.

red = ground truth; green = data-driven flow, yellow = averaged scene flow

Performance on Rare Events

Figure 9. Comparison of average tracking errors when tracking people in rare crowd events based on 21 tracks and $k = 3$.

Social Force Model

Helbing and Molnár (1995). “Social force model for pedestrian dynamics”. Physical Review E 51 (5): 4282–4286

Social forces represent similar information as floor fields.

But one important distinction: working in an agent-centered point of view rather than a scene-centered one.

In other words, microscopic rather than macroscopic.

Social Force Model

you are
here

Social Force Model

Case Study

Pellegrini, Ess, Schindler, van Gool *You'll Never Walk Alone: Modeling Social Behavior for Multi-target Tracking* ICCV 2009

Consider two moving pedestrians.

What is their point of closest approach?

(assuming they move with constant velocity)

Case Study

Pellegrini, Ess, Schindler, van Gool *You'll Never Walk Alone: Modeling Social Behavior for Multi-target Tracking* ICCV 2009

$$p_1(t) = s_1 + t v_1 \quad p_2(t) = s_2 + t v_2$$

$$t^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{(t>0)} \| p_2(t) - p_1(t) \|^2$$

$$c_1 = s_1 + t^* v_1 \quad c_2 = s_2 + t^* v_2$$

Case Study

Pellegrini, Ess, Schindler, van Gool *You'll Never Walk Alone: Modeling Social Behavior for Multi-target Tracking* ICCV 2009

intuition: we want to adjust v_1 and v_2 to keep a “comfortable” distance d_{12} between them, while maintaining roughly the original desired directions and speeds.

Case Study

Pellegrini, Ess, Schindler, van Gool *You'll Never Walk Alone: Modeling Social Behavior for Multi-target Tracking* ICCV 2009

the new velocities are found
by numerical optimization

Model Yields Intuitive Behavior

Pellegrini, Ess, Schindler, van Gool *You'll Never Walk Alone: Modeling Social Behavior for Multi-target Tracking* ICCV 2009

Depending on distance between s_2 and s_3 , pedestrian s_1 will either try to pass between them, or around them.

Pedestrian Fingering

Helbing's social force model also predicts “fingering” in areas of bidirectional motion. People tend to follow others to minimize collisions (maximize throughput).

Green: leftward moving. Red: rightward moving,

Fingering Effect

collective behavior emerges from independent decisions

<-- Leftward

Rightward -->

Density by image row
Green (leftward); Red (rightward)

Collective Locomotion

- **Find small groups traveling together**
 - Sociological hypothesis: validating that the majority of people in the crowd cluster in small groups
 - Public safety: improving situation awareness and emergency response during public disturbances

McPhail and Wohlstein, 1982

- Group membership is determined via a cascaded set of three tests:
 - ① Any two people who are within 7 feet of each other and not separated by another individual are considered to be **contiguous**
 - ② Any two **contiguous** people whose speeds are the same to within .5 feet per second are judged to have the **same speed**
 - ③ Any two contiguous people traveling at the **same speed** whose directions of motion are the same to within 3 degrees are judged to have the **same direction**
- Another procedure tests whether a new individual should be added to an existing group to form a larger group
- Limitations
 - Hundreds of person-hours needed to hand code just minutes of film
 - Difficult for dense crowds/long sequences

Automated Group Testing by Agglomerative Clustering

W.Ge, R.Collins and B.Ruback, "Vision-based Analysis of Small Groups in Pedestrian Crowds,"
IEEE Trans Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, Vol 34(5), 2012, pp.1003-1016.

“distance” is based on spatial proximity
and velocity coherence

Sample Results

note: computer only sees this view!

Evaluation reveals substantial agreement between computer-generated groupings and those found by human coders (ground truth)

	match rate	$\chi^2(4, 248)$	Cohen's κ
trichotomous	85%	219.98	.69
dichotomous	89%	138.26	.75

$p < .001$

Robert Collins
Penn State

More Grouping Results

Likely Group Shapes

Are some group configurations more likely than others? Of course!

Analysis of Group Shape

Figure 5.14. The configurations of groups of size three are aligned with respect to their group centers and moving directions. The three members are plotted with three different colors after a data association procedure that matches points across different configurations. Edges indicating the group configuration are omitted for clarity.

Analysis of Group Shape

analyzing groups
of three people

Procrustes Analysis, first four modes of variation

Research Questions

Is multitarget tracking of human crowds any different than tracking crowds of animals? bats? cells?